
IMPACT OF BUDGET DEFICIT AND INTEREST RATE ON INFLATION IN NIGERIA ECONOMY 1980 - 2023: AN INVERSE RELATIONSHIP ANALYSIS

¹TORDEE, BARIKUI, Dept. of Accountancy, Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, P. M. B 20 Bori, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

²FELIX IGBARA, PhD & ³NWANYANWU, H. DENNIS. PhD,
General Studies, Kenule Beeson Saro Wiwa Polytechnic
P. M. B. 20 Bori, Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

Abstract

This paper investigates an inverse relationship analysis of impact of budget deficit and interest on inflation in Nigeria economy between 1980 and 2023. The paper was predicated on "Overhang Debt Theory." Materials for the study were obtained from secondary sources, which include Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, textbooks and published journals. The data for analysis was sourced from CBN's statistical bulletin. Augmented Dickey Fuller, unit root test and Vector auto regression model were adopted in the data analysis.. The results revealed that there was evidence of stationarity among the variables applied in this study. Thus, an increase in budget deficits will affect interest and inflation rates in Nigeria.

Key words: *Impact. Budget Deficit, Interest, Inflation, Economy, Inverse Relationship.*

1.0 Introduction

Budgets deficits are often or to a larger extent attributed to rising public expenditure over public revenue. The policy of the government can also be used to influence the pattern of expenditure with the sole aim of promoting economic growth. Deficits are common features in most developing countries including Nigeria. The economic response of such deficits to inflation and interest rates constitute a major source of concern to economic planners and policy makers in any nation.

In the views of Adewuyi (2000), he posited that capital expenditure in the form of public investment contributes to growth by making available basic infrastructure and public good that are viewed to be crucial for development. He further asserted that increase in money supply may eventually lead to increase in price which is referred to as inflation and this is known as a measure of financial instability. But in most countries, interest rates are decided by those who are in control of the financial institutions and as such, CBN controls interest rates through the banks. But excessive expenditure by the government can be very detrimental because an economy that is experiencing fast growth due to high government expenditure lead to involved in hyperinflation. Furthermore, interest rates directly affect the credit market this is because higher interest rates make borrowing more costly. And as such, changing interest rates makes it possible for CBN to achieve some level of stability in the economy thus, inflation and interest rates are linked and are always referenced in macro-economics.

Statement of Problem

Budget deficit propels increase interest rate which crowds out small scale investor who are looking for micro-credits for investment. The effect may be that the government could be trying to fight a particular economic problem. This could result to the adoption of monetary policy framework of the government. It depends on whether the government is fighting to control inflation or unemployment. In this case, two types of monetary policies are important: Contractionary or expansionary monetary policy. All are geared towards stabilizing the economy by increasing aggregate output increases by a multiple of the increase in investment in the case of unemployment or leading to Price level falls in the case of inflation in the economy. If these assertions are true, it raised the question of how have budget deficit and interest rate positively impacted on unemployment and inflation in Nigeria. It is against this backdrop that this paper conducts an investigation on the impact of budget deficit and interest rate on inflation in Nigeria economy 1980 – 2023. This study therefore seeks to establish the impact of interest and inflation rates on budget deficits in Nigeria.

2.0 Conceptual Clarifications

Clarification of concept helps to throw more light into the meaning of a word being used or terminology in a study as contained in the keyword list. The concepts of the terminologies contained in the title of the paper are explained below:

Concept of Budget Deficit: Nigeria as a developing country is plagued by increasing government expenditure and unmatched government revenue Several factors could be responsible for these such as level of economic development, slow growth of government revenue, instability of government revenue, poor government control over expenditure and the extent of government participation in the economy. Although a wide range of policies were put in place to correct this pertinent problem, such policy was meant to compress public expenditure and to raise taxes and to find other sources of generating public revenue (Yekini,

2001). But several arguments have been put forward on budget deficits, one of such argument is based on the premise that direct involvement of government in the economy is influenced largely by the Keynesian public expenditure led growth model. But Onoh, (2007) posited that In Nigeria, public sector expenditure has hardly been tailored to match anticipated or projected revenue of government.

This has been responsible for the government to balance its budget or to pursue a limited deficit fiscal policy which is viewed to be the bane of the Nigeria Economy (Egwaikhide, 1996, Gbosi, 2005, Onoh, 2007), Onoh (2007) further added that the economy is further affected by double digit inflation as a result of excessive deficit fiscal operation to the considered in this study. Although, the government uses budget to plan and control their fiscal affairs, to a larger extent this has not been the case in Nigeria, as a result of this the profile of Nigerian budget deficits have reached a state of serious concern to policy makers and economic planners because fiscal deficits have attributed to government spending over and above public revenue which is viewed to have damaging effect on the economy.

Interest: Interest rate is viewed as the price paid for borrowing money and as such interest rate represents an important monetary policy tool. But in the views of the classical theory, the rate of interest is determined by the supply of and demand for capital. The supply of capital is thus governed by the time preference and the demand for capital. Jhingan, (1997) further asserted that capital is subject to the law of variable proportion which is based on the principle that higher rate of interest will affect the demand for capital and high demand of capital will imply lower interest rate and as such the demand for capital is inversely related to the rate of interest. We can therefore conclude that the rate of interest is determined by the interaction of demand and supply of loanable fund attributed to loanable fund theory. It is important to mention that the demand for loanable fund has primarily three sources which are stated as government, business purposes and the individual while the supply of loanable fund comes from savings, dishoarding and bank credit. Thus, the higher the rate of interest the greater will be the inducement to save. This is possible as it will also discourage hoarding which will be attracted to higher interest rates. But Keynes viewed interest rate as the reward of not hoarding money the reward for parting with liquidity.

2.1 Determinants of Interest Rates: Determinants of interest rates are supply of money and demand for money. The supply of money refers to the total quantity of money while the second determinant of money which is tagged liquidity preference is the desire to hold cash. In the views of Keynes, interest rate is the premium which has to be offered to induce people to alter their wealth in other portfolios than hoarding of money. Towards this backdrop, Keynes held the view that there are three motives for holding money which are transactionary, precautionary and speculative. But the one that affects interest rate more is speculative. In the views of Jhingan (2010), he asserted that money held for speculative purposes can be invested at an opportune moment in interest bearing bonds and securities. And as such interest rates are useful in gauging the financial markets conditions (Gbosi, 2005). It is important to mention that the structure of interest rates changes is always relative to shifts in market portfolio of the financial institutions. Thus, the direction and magnitude of changes in interest rates are of primary importance to economic planners and policy makers (Tauner & Devereau, 1993).

Concept of Inflation: Inflation has been viewed as a highly controversial term with several modifications and definitions. The neo classical viewed inflation as a monetary phenomenon while the economists posited that inflation is a continuous rise in prices (Okechukwu and Adoghor, (2000), Samuelson and Nordhaus, (2005), Gbosi (2005) and Onoh (2007). But, it

is important to mention that a sustained rise in price maybe of various magnitude depending on the rate of rise in prices, this magnitude could be; Creeping inflation, this form of inflation is viewed to be slow and in terms of speed it is not more than 3 percent per annum. This form of inflation is regarded as safe and essential for economic growth. Trotting Inflation, This is a situation where the rate of inflation rises moderately while the annual inflation rate is a single digit. This is viewed to be a warning signal for the government to begin to put on ground policies to check its rise. Running Inflation: When price rise rapidly, at the rate of 10 to 20 percent per annum. Such rate of inflation affects all facets of the economy. Its control entails strong fiscal and monetary measures. Hyperinflation: When prices rises rapidly or very fast at double or triple digit rates, it is called galloping inflation. But in reality, hyperinflation, is a rate of inflation when it becomes immeasurable and uncontrollable. Therefore, as inflation proceeds and the real value of currencies fluctuates and utterly disordered, it makes possible for the value of wealth to degenerate (Keynes, 1936). Towards this back drop, we can say; that inflation affects redistribution of income and wealth among different groups, distortions in the relative prices and output of different goods and services or sometimes in output and employment on the economy as a whole.

Several controversies have surrounded budget deficits, inflation and interest rates in Nigeria. Despite these controversies, there had being no proper relationship between the variables listed above. This is because the Ricardian view believes that deficits do not matter because an increase in government spending is equivalent to a future increase in tax liabilities. And as such, budget deficits do not affect interest and inflation rates. This view is supported by Darrat (1990), Cheng (1998), Gbosi (2005) and Jhinghan (2010). While the Keynesians held the view that budget deficits influences interest rates and inflation rates which was supported by Laumas (1989) and Dua (1993). While Allen and Smith (1983) and Tanner and Devereux (1993) posited that budget deficits are related to either inflation or interest rates, it further implies that deficits are inflationary. Against this backdrop, this study will investigate the impact of interest and inflation rates on budget deficits in Nigeria.

Inverse Relationship: this appears in a situation of two type of relations between two variables where an increase in one variable leads to a decrease in the other variable, and vice versa. In other words, as one variable goes up, the other variable goes down and as one variable goes down, the other variable goes up. This means movement of the two variables is always in opposite directions.

Overhang Debt Theory

However, this paper hinges on Overhang Debt Theory formulated to support public debt burden According to Overhang Debt Kruman, (198), overhang Debt Theory explains the possibility of larger government debt than the repayment ability of the country will be face discouragement due to expect cost of servicing the debt. This discouragement will affect the possibility of further incurring foreign and domestic investments. Future investors will be discouraged due to the understanding that they may experience more taxes as they produce to enable the government service her hanging public debts. Therefore, more productions will attract more taxation hence, their less willingness to incur cots of investment just to increase output in the future (Gordn & Cosimo, 2018). Public debt accumulation is considered as future output tax and savings and investment reduction incentive. Debt service requirement reduces available fund for investment and it is a liquidity binding constraint on debt with possibility of restraining investment thereby retarding economic growth and development (Coccia, 2017). It is the suggestion of the theory that effect on the growth through capital accumulation or growth of productivity may occur. The bottom-line is that the huge fund used in servicing huge public debt drains resources that would have been made available for

investment in most critical sectors of the economy. For developing nations, huge debt servicing reduces resources and dims possible growth. Increased debt burden propels capital flight and creates devaluation risk, taxation and the zeal to protect real financial assets value while capital flight depletes domestic savings investment thereby reducing both economic growth, debt serving capacity and tax base.

2.1 Empirical Literature

Several studies have tried to relate budget deficit to inflation in the economy. The work of Kasali, Ahmad and Ean, (2016) widened the discussion on this topic in their study on determinants of Microcredit Access: Empirical Analysis from South-West Nigeria. Focus of the study was on accessibility of micro-finance credit in Nigeria. The paper adopted Descriptive statistics and Logit Regression Model analysis. It was discovered that Age, Household size, Business worth, Skill/Experience, Education level, Assets, Health standard. It was also found that living standard and income are significant in determining the accessibility of the poor to microfinance loan. Impact of microfinance lending on the Nigeria economic growth was investigated by Obasi, Chukwuka and Akwawa, (2014). The study focused on microfinance lending to micro, small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. The paper adopted programme designs and numerical structure response in implementation and performance model. It was discovered that the microfinance loans have not gone deep enough to ensure a clean break from community and commercial banking practices. Aero and Ogundipe, (2018) tried to ascertain a feasible threshold of fiscal deficit and economic growth in Nigeria. Focus of the study was on optimal fiscal deficit level using the Threshold. The paper adopted Threshold Autoregressive model in the analysis. It was discovered that a significant negative relationship exists between fiscal deficits, financial depth and economic growth in Nigeria. The study further found that study established a threshold level of 5% which is conducive for economic growth at a lag of 1 year, for the Nigerian economy.

The economic performance of budget deficit in Nigeria was investigated by Fagbohun Akinola, (2017). The study focus was on budget deficit and external reserves. The study adopted the least square method for the data analysis. the result discovered that both budget deficits and external reserves have positive and significant impact on capita income, whereas bank rate and money supply have indirect and insignificant on the same per capita income. Unfortunately, budget deficits, money supply and external reserves don't create growth that enhance employment rate in Nigeria It was further found that that bank rate reduces unemployment rate. Similarly, budget deficits, money supply and bank rate cause price instability but the result of bank rate reports the opposite. Jakpa and Osho-Itsueli, (2020) investigated deficit financing and macroeconomic performance: the Nigeria experience. Focus of the study was on deficit financing and performance of the economy. The ARDL model was implored for the data analysis. the result revealed that there is long run relationship between the variables, and from the estimates of the long run equation, all the variables having a significant effect on the economy with domestic money supply inducing positive impact

Effect of budget deficit and infrastructural financing on the economy of Nigeria was studied by Umezuruike and Ariwa, (2024). Focus of the study was on budget deficit implications on the economy. The paper adopted Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) for its estimation. The result revealed that the total government deficit exerted a negative and significant effect on the economic growth of Nigeria. Government expenditure on transportation, government expenditure on health, and gross capital formation had a positive and significant effect on

economic growth. It was further found that government expenditure on education had a negative and significant effect on the economic growth of Nigeria.

Agu and Chukwuebuka, (2024) investigated the effect of deficit budget financing sources on inflation rate in Nigeria. The study focused on external debt, ways and means advances, and treasury bills. Ordinary Least Square multiple regression technique was adopted in the data analysis. It was discovered that external debt and treasury bills have a significant effect on inflation rate in Nigeria. It was further found that ways and means advances have a positive and significant effect on inflation rate in Nigeria.

3.0 Methodology

The objective of this study is to examine the impact of interest and inflation rates on budgets deficits. We intend to apply econometric view of data analysis. We will therefore present an econometric model which is based on standard economic theory by examining the time series properties of the variables by using Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test. The vector auto regression model will also be applied because it can be transformed into vector error correction mechanism and it is not vulnerable to simultaneity. It can be used to predict and forecast the parameter restrictions. Materials for the study were sources from secondary Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, textbooks and published journals.

3.1 Empirical Results and Discussion

The data used in this paper consists of yearly time series data of three macro-economic variables for the period from 1980-2012. These aggregates are budget deficits, interest and inflation rates.

In fig 1 above, the data for analysis was collected from the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The data were analyzed using the E -views. The series were transformed by taking their natural logarithms. We can therefore say that the series appear to be stationary at all levels.

Table 1: Augmented Dickey -Fuller (ADF) and Philips Perron (PP) Tests for unit root
3.1.1 Test for Unit Root

Variable	ADF tau-statistic							
	Level		First difference		Level		First difference	
	Constant	p-value	Constant	p-value	Constant	p-value	Constant	p-value
Ln/NF	-3.3667	0.0199	-6.2047	0.0000	-.32717	0.0249	-13.1853	0.0000
Ln/NF	-3.0849	0.0379	-5.7124	0.0001	-2.9748	0.0481	-9.4783	0.0000
LnIBDF	-2.7496	0.0770	-7.7503	0.0000	-2.7934	0.0704	-12.6251	0.0000

The table shown above presents the Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) and Philip Perrons (PP) tests for unit root. The tests are performed first in the level of the series and on their first differences. The lag order selection of ADF test is based on the Schwarz information criteria with a maximum lag of 8. The PP test is estimated using the Bartlett Kernel method with Newey West Band width automatic selection. The t-statistic rejected the null hypothesis of unit root at 10% level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that Ln/NF and Ln/NT are non-stationary were rejected at 5% level of significance providing strong evidence of stationarity, which implies that all the series are stationary and integrated at the same order.

Table 2: Residual based co-integration test p -values are in parenthesis

3.1.2 Engle-Granger Residual Based Cointegration Test

Dependent variable	Tau -statistic	z-statistic
LnBDF	-2.816883(0.3554)	-14.06444(0.2694)
Ln/NF	-3.450589(0.1411)	-17.74686(0.1199)
Ln/NT	-2.425168(0.5406)	-6.779104(0.7770)

The table above shows the Engle granger residual based integration test, this is a single equation approach for testing whether the series are co -integrated. The tests shows that both the test, tau statistic fail to reject the null hypothesis of no co -integration at 10%. This is further supported by the Z-statistic which shows no co-integration meaning that the series do not share the same stochastic trend.

Table 3: Johansen test for cointegration p -values are in parenthesis

3.1.3 Johansen Co-Integration Test

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace statistic	Max-Eigen Statistic
None	0.364587	23.91163(0.2042)	14.05790 (0.3603)
At most 1	0.210836	9.853733(0.2921)	7.340209 (0.4497)
At most 2	0.077881	2.513524(0.1129)	2.513524(0.1129)

This test is carried out to support the results obtained while applying the residual based test. This approach applies two statistics namely the trace and max Eigen statistics. The trace statistic is used to test the null hypothesis meaning that there is r co-integrating relations against the alternative hypothesis that there is K co-integrating relationship. The Max Eigen tests the null hypothesis of r co-integrating relations against the alternative hypothesis of r + 1 co-integrating relationship in the system. Based on the table above, there is no evidence of co-integration among the variables. These findings supports the results obtained from the single equation residual based co-integration test leading to the test for VAR.

Table 4: Unrestricted VAR estimated with std. errors in bracket and t -statistic in sq. bracket
3.1.4 Unrestricted Vector Autoregressive (Var) Model

	LnBDF	Ln/NF	Ln/NT
Ln/BDFt-1	0.568265 (0.16516) (3.44076)	0.011883 (0.04767) (0.24925)	0.007247 (0.01636) (0.44287)
Ln/NFt4	-0.144290 (0.58617) (-0.24616)	0.453698 (0.16920) (2.68137)	0.017745 (0.05808) (0.30553)
Ln/NTt4	-0.439817 (1.39284) (-0.31577)	0.056641 (0.40206) (0.14088)	0.580946 (0.13801) (4.20945)
C	5.805382 (4.28570) (1.35459)	1.214967 (1.23712) (0.98209)	1.139098 (0.42465) (2.68244)

The table above shows the results of the estimated unrestricted VAR model. Based on our previous results we included a constant term and one lagged value of each variable in each equation of the VAR model, implying that we have a total of 12 coefficients in the model. The results shows that most of the figure obtained are not significant at a conventional level.

Table 5: Lag order Selection Asterisks * indicates lag order selected by each criterion
3.1.5 Lag Length Criteria

Lag	AIC	SIC
0	7.529911	7.668684
1	7.105308*	7.660400*
2	7.160349	8.131760

The table above is used to determine the appropriate number of lags for the VAR equation. This is done by comparing two information criteria AIC and SIC with a maximum of 2 lags. The results indicates that both the AIC and SIC criteria select of lag order 1 is appropriate.

Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

Figure 2. Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

The graph above is used to check whether the estimated VAR is stationary or stable. Where all the roots lie inside the unit circle, it implies that the estimated VAR is stable of which the estimated VAR satisfies the stability condition indicating that all our results are valid.

3.1.6 Pair Wise Granger Causality Test

Table 6: Granger causality test

Dependent variable: LnBDF		Dependent variable: TLn/NF		Dependent variable: Ln/NT	
Excluded	Chi-square	Excluded	Chi-square	Excluded	Chi-square
Ln /NF	0.060595(0.805)	Ln /BDF	0.062128 (0.8032)	Ln /BDF	0.196137 (0.6579)
Ln/NT	0.099711 (0.7522)	Ln /NT	0.019846 (0.8880)	Ln /NT	0.093346 (0.7600)
All	0.186881 (0.9108)	All	0.092362 (0.09549)	All	0.273692 (0.8721)

This test is used to establish if there is a causal relationship between two or more endogenous variables in the VAR model. From the table above, the variables in each of the equation is not significant. This implies that no endogenous variable in the model can be treated as an exogenous variable.

**Pulse Response Function
 Response to Cholesky One S.D Innovations ± 2 S.E.
 Response of BDF to BDF**

The impulse response function is dynamic analysis that traces the effects of a onetime change in one (endogenous) variable on the current and future values of all variables in the VAR system. As we trace the effect of one time shock to budget deficits for only three years. Since the response variables (interest and inflation rates) are controlled by the monetary authorities, the graph above shows response to one standard deviation shock to budget deficits; inflation reacts negatively in the first year but becomes positive after the second year while interest rate reacts positively in the first year and becomes stable before the second year.

3.1.7 Variance Decomposition

Period	S.E	LnBDF	LnINF	LnINt
1	2.430981	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000
2	2.798758	99.71803	0.140599	0.141368
3	2.907367	99.40819	0.282156	0.309658
4	2.941195	99.19197	0.373203	0.434827
5	2.951835	99.06983	0.420795	0.509377
6	2.955184	99.00921	0.442719	0.548072

The table above provides information about the relative contribution of each endogenous variable in the VAR system to the variation in budget deficit. From the table above both inflation and interest rates accounts for less than 1% of the variation in budget deficit throughout the forecast period. This is also possible since the three variables do not share the same stochastic trend which corresponds with the result obtained from the granger causality test.

4.0 Summary and Conclusion

In this paper, we investigated the impact of interest and inflation rates on budget deficits in Nigeria. The reason for this study is that Nigeria have over the years (1980-2012) experienced high deficits. The empirical methodology that was applied in this study is the econometric analysis.

4.1 Summary of results

There is a strong evidence of stationarity and as such the variables are integrated at the same order. Thus, an increase in budget deficit will affect interest and inflation rates in Nigeria. In the analysis, it was discovered that all the variables are stable which implies that our results are valid. Since interest and inflation rates have some level of control through the monetary authorities, there are standard deviation shocks to budget deficits in Nigeria. This also brings to bear the impact of the monetary authorities in their position to control their level of deficits. Thus, this study conforms to the previous studies of Ahking and Milner (1983), King and Plosser (1986), Dua (1993) and Cheng (1998).

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were put forward.

1. Policies should be put on ground that will bring about some level of fiscal discipline on projects that are only people oriented.
2. There should be a proper mix between monetary and fiscal policies due to their impact on interest and inflation rates in Nigeria.
3. The government can channel her borrowing through the financial markets.
4. Since the monetary authorities are concerned with monetary policies that will also include constant checks on inflation and interest rates, there is the need for a complete autonomy of the central bank of Nigeria.

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